

THE IMPACT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES ON THE EFFICIENCY OF MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This article analyzes the role of marketing in the development of the enterprise, the concept, essence and goals of marketing, the main elements of marketing activities, the concept and methods of profit management of the enterprise and the development of marketing activities in the enterprise.

Key words

Net occupancy, marketing, profit, management, net present value, creative management, effectiveness, economic activity.

Introduction

The marketing strategy includes four areas: product, price, distribution channels and promotion methods. Marketing activities are very diverse, and are classified on the following grounds: by production and technological criteria, by commodity-market or geographical determinism, by the sequence of product promotion on the market, by the methods of entering international markets or interacting with competing companies. Depending on the production and technological criteria, companies effectively apply the strategy of "technological push-in", the strategy of "market pull-in" or the strategy of cost reduction. According to the criterion of geographical determinism, the marketing strategy can be national (large countries), regional, multinational, global. According to the criterion of commodity-market determinism, the marketing strategy may be aimed at market development (increasing sales in new markets), narrow assortment, diversification (sometimes concentric, horizontal, conglomerate), expansion of the assortment or individualization of consumers. According to the sequence of promotion of goods to markets, marketing strategy can be expressed in simultaneous entry into all available markets or be gradual (cascade marketing strategy). Under the first option, company conducts an aggressive pricing and advertising policy, investing huge amounts of money during an entry period. Such a marketing strategy is possible for large companies, and medium and small businesses most often use a cascade strategy, mastering the market gradually (Tkachenko, 2012).

The main task of marketing is to achieve its strategic goals, comprehensive development and ensuring the greatest sustainability in the company's activities. In addition to these tasks, as a result of marketing activities, tasks related to providing the company with reliable, timely and reliable information on the market, goods, consumers and competitors are solved; creating a product that best meets the needs of the consumer, the capabilities of the company; influencing the consumer, demand and market.

To achieve these objectives, it is necessary to conduct marketing research that shows the marketing situation facing the company based on data, analysis and a report on the results.

These studies should be based on information about production volumes, which reflect the capacity of the main equipment, which reflects the possibilities of the volume of production. If we consider the production volumes for several years, this helps to identify the trend of its development. In the information about the volume of capital investment, which reflects the state and prospects of production, we can find out about products, if there is an increase, it indicates an increase in demand, the need to develop its production and improve quality, and the decrease tells us about a decrease in interest in products and a reduction in production.

A list of data for marketing research is also needed:

1. According to information about the production technology.
2. Information about the raw materials for the production of the product.
3. Data on technological and processing equipment according to its technical level.
4. Indicators and characteristics of technical and economic indicators of products, including price.
5. Information on the areas of application of this product and its competing products.
6. Data on the direction and content of scientific research.
7. General assessment of the economic efficiency of the product.
8. Other data on the state of production and consumption of the product.

The necessary order of work should consist in finding and identifying the largest consumers of the product who will be interested in it. The next stage should be the development and distribution of questionnaires, which will contain the necessary questions concerning the product, namely technical characteristics and needs. At the last stage, the product is evaluated according to its compliance and requirements based on the analysis of consumer questionnaires by experts.

Such a study is conducted to obtain the necessary list of knowledge about the product, what effect a new product will have, social or economic, demand, need for development, and the ability to correlate the volume of production and demand. Marketing research includes a number of stages (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stages of marketing research (created by author)

In the stages of marketing research, it can be seen that at the very beginning it is necessary to identify the problem.

Marketing specialists are often asked only the facts: about falling sales volumes, falling market share. Only these are symptoms, but they need to identify the cause of their occurrence. A concretized and clearly expressed problem is the key to the successful conduct of marketing research.

At the first stage, it is necessary to study this problem, get information about the area under study, and create an algorithm for work.

This algorithm can be:

1. Study of the necessary literature
2. Conducting a survey of experts
3. Group discussions.

To identify the problem, it is necessary to clarify the purpose of the study. These goals are divided into the following:

1. Search (collection of preliminary data).
2. Descriptive (describing a certain phenomenon).
3. Experimental (used to test cause-and-effect relationships).

The main task of the stage is the influence of existing problem on the problem of research. To formulate a study and clearly define the problem, we need to collect and analyze information that is necessary for decision-making. This collection of information should begin with analysis of secondary data.

Secondary information is data about the object of research obtained from the source as a result of marketing research, which allows to refine and optimize them. The main advantages and disadvantages of secondary information are reflected in Table 1.

Advantages	Disadvantages
inexpensive collection of information	the information may be unnecessary for research purposes
quick collection of information	the information may be outdated
there are often a large number of sources of information	methods of collecting information are unknown
it is possible to contain information that the company cannot obtain itself	incomplete research results may be published
	information can be contradictory and unreliable

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of secondary information (created by author, 2023)

This information is located in the sources:

1. Internal (company reports, profits and losses, costs, cash flow, accounts receivable and accounts payable, etc.).
2. External (statistics of economic, financial, social survey; market overview, publications in government agencies, in economics, trade, business, marketing, etc.).

After collecting secondary information, it is necessary to collect primary information.

Primary information is data about an object received directly from a source to solve specific problems.

Analysis of secondary and primary information is necessary to simplify the results of the study, making it more organized and understandable.

Based on such an analysis of the marketing research, recommendations are prepared-suggestions about the future actions of the company based on the collected data, and are submitted to the management in writing. The report on the results of the study is a feedback from the management, which is responsible for using the results (Mashenko, 2010).

Conclusion

From this chapter, it can be concluded that in today's world, marketing is an integral part of the success of any organization. It denotes the activity of studying consumer groups and conquering the market. As the relations between the subjects of market relations change and become more complicated, the importance of marketing is constantly increasing. Marketing pushes to improve the product, makes it clear what is more important for the consumer: convenience, aesthetics, accessibility, quality or a combination of some parameters. And thanks to this, not only to correctly build a promotion strategy, but also to detect imperfections of the product from the client's point of view.

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